

Women Self Help Groups: An Emancipatory Measure - A Study of Guntur District of Andhra Pradesh

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Abstract

The gender issues were subsumed by the concern for poverty, unemployment and Backwardness in India's early rural development efforts. Education, Employment and Empowerment are the three E's and income generation assets for the advancement building and development of women. Empowerment is a multi-dimensional process, which should enable the individuals as a group of individuals to realize their full identity and powers in all sphere of life. Empowerment of women may also mean equal status, opportunity and freedom to women in order to develop themselves. Self-Help Groups are considered as one of the most significant tools through micro-credit, micro-finance to participation of approach for the socio-economic empowerment of women. Micro finance and micro credit through Self-Help Groups as a solution for the multiple problems created by external finance and credit for development activities. It paves way for mobilization, collection and pooling of local resources and for its distribution on the need basis. As the resources under distribution are contributed by the people, their proper use, repayment and recycling are ensured by the contributing group and the community. It presents an ideal set up for promoting self-help and eliminating the culture of dependence. This paper is an attempt in analyzing the role played by the self-help groups in promoting women participation and empowerment of socio-economic development in the society.

Keywords: Gender, Self-Help Groups, Participation, Resources, Empowerment.

Introduction

India is a country with an area of 3.3 million square kilometers, as per 2011, we have 1,210 million population who live in nearly eight thousand urban areas and more than six lakhs rural areas, which more than 70 percent of the people live in rural areas. As the second thickly populace country in the world after China. A latest survey on poverty shows that 37 percent of 1.35 billion Indian Population continue to live below the poverty line. More than 22 percent of the total rural population and 15 percent of the urban population survive financial tight spot.

Women constitutes nearly fifty percent of total population and eighty percent of the women population live in rural areas in our country. Women, as in almost all developing countries in the world, are the neglected section in the context of development. In the societies of earlier period, women as a class did not enjoy quall rights

and opportunities as men had absolute control over social attitudes and customs towards women. In spite of several measures undertaken for their upliftment, women continue to lag behind men in different spheres.

As per the Canadian International Development Agency (CIDA) viewed that “empowerment is about people – both women and men – taking control over their lives: setting their own agenda, gaining skills, increasing self-confidence, solving problems, and developing self-reliance. It is both a process and an outcome”.

Suguna. B (2002) has defines women empowerment as process whereby women able to organise themselves to increase self-reliance, to assert their independent right to make choices and to control resources which will assist in challenging and eliminating their own subordination. Empowering women basically means to provide them opportunities to live and work “With dignity”.

Both national and international policy documents have emphasis on the empowerment of women to rectify this situation empowerment of women is a necessary basic conditions for socio-economic development of our society. Strategies made to be designed to enhance the capacity of women and empower them to meet deprivation.

Hoshemi (1996) developed five indicators to measure women’s empowerment: mobility, economic security, ability to make larger purchases, realize freedom from domination within the family and political and legal awareness and involvement in political campaigning and protests with this in mind. An attempt is made in the following situation to measure empowerment of women respondents.

Mayoux (1998) and Rajasekhar (2002) stated that the micro finance activities undertaken by the self help groups are expected to contribute significant to poverty alleviation and empowerment of members in socio-economic and political spheres. However, these activities are considered potentially supportive as an effective means to reduce poverty but not of extreme poverty.

In Indian, majority of women has rendering the different services in agriculture and alternative activities in rural areas. However, the conditions under which these women work have not changed much during the decade of 1970s to 1980s. Therefore, the Integrated Rural Development Programme (IRDP) was introduced in 1978 as an economic programme for providing opportunities for supplemental income to women through allied activities in rural areas. In 1982-83, Development of Women and Children in Rural Areas (DWCRA) was introduced as a pilot project in 50 selected district and one district in each union territory, previously the programme called Basic Services in Rural Development (BSRD). Development of women and Children in Rural Areas Primary thrust has been on the formation of groups of 10-15 Women from poor households at the village level, for delivery of services like credit and skill training and infrastructural support for self-employment. In April 1999, six rural development programmes including Development of Women and Children in Rural Areas (DWCRA) were integrated and the nomenclature of the programme was Swarnajayanti the Gram Swarazgar yojana (SGSY) which focuses on Self Help Groups (SHGs) approach. Since, the SGSY has been changed to National Rural Livelihood Mission.

This institutional arrangements that are providing financial services at the micro level are called Microfinance Institutions (MFIs), Micro-credit and Self-Help Groups (SHGs). Asian Development Bank defines Microfinance Institutions as “Institutions whose major business is the provision of microfinance services. Microfinance Institutions have been operating under different legal systems and structures like non-profit Microfinance Institutions, Cooperatives, Registered Banking Institutions, and Government Organizations.

Intervention of Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOS)

In the past few decades voluntary organizations have made notable contribution in the eradication of poverty through empowerment of women in rural areas. Endeavors made by their bodies in different parts of the nation are claimed to have served significantly in formulating and strengthening the current strategies of rural development. The voluntary service has been integral part of Indian culture since time immemorial. Today the voluntary organizations have playing a significant role in the implementation of their own programmes and supplementing of the government programmes like awareness programmes, education programmes, training programmes, formation of self help groups, micro finance and micro credit to motivate rural people in firsthand knowledge to acquire latest technology and to improve their standard of living by involving women participation in income-generating activities in rural areas.

Intervention of International Bodies

According to World Bank Report (2001) today, in the context of United Nations Reform, virtually all United Nations departments, different heads of state, Governments with special assistance and attention of World Health Organization (WHO); United Nations International Children's Emergency Fund (UNICEF); United Nation Education, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO), World Bank, International Monetary Fund (IMF), International Labour Organization (ILO); World Trade Organization (WTO); United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) and other concerned bilateral and multilateral organizations have introduced various programmes and policies, appropriate technologies for women empowerment.

In September 2000, building upon a decade of major United Nations Conferences and Summits, world leaders came together at United Headquarters in New York to adopt' the United Nations Millennium Declaration, committing their nations to a New Global Partnership to reduce extreme poverty and setting out a series of time-bound targets with a deadline of 2015 that have become known as the Millennium Development Goals.

The study assumes importance in the context of existing the role and status of self-help groups in women empowerment and development activities at grass-root level. In this context, the researcher shows much interest in studying self-help groups in Kopalle Village, Guntur District of Andhra Pradesh has been chosen by formulating the necessary objectives.

Objectives of Study

The aim of the study is to understand importance of self-help groups for women empowerment in the rural areas for rural development. In order to study the following objectives have been formulated.

1. To examine the socio-economic characteristics of the study respondents.
2. To examine the impact of self-help groups on women empowerment.
3. To give suggestions for effective functioning of self-help groups on women empowerment in rural areas.

Methodology

The methodological aspect of the present study are with reference to selection of the district, selection of the village, universe and sample, sources of data collection and tools of analysis as follows.

Selection of the District and the Village

The state of Andhra Pradesh has three regions: Rayalaseema, South Coastal Andhra, North Coastal Andhra. The Kopalle Village in Guntur District of south coastal Andhra region has been selected purposefully. Though it has many self-help groups, which are formed and functioning self-help groups in Kopalle village are reputed and well organizing for in promoting women empowerment. In order to study 18 self-help groups out of 43 groups and each group consisting 10 members and total 180 members has been selected. A purposive sampling procedure has been adopted so as to select the above self-help groups. To examine the impact of benefited self-help groups since the year 2014 were considered.

Tools of Data Collection

The data for the present study is collected from the sources of primary and secondary data. The primary data were collected by Focused Groups Discussion (FGD) and Interview Method covering the aspects of socio-economic profile of the beneficiaries of self-help groups. The secondary data were obtained from the published and unpublished reports.

Tools of Data Analysis

A simple statistical tools such as averages, percentages has been used for the purpose of analyzing the data.

Discussion

Profile of Women Members of Self-Help Groups

Table 1 Distribution of the Respondents by Caste wise

Sl. No.	Category of caste	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Schedule Caste	60	33.33
2	Schedule Tribe	30	16.67
3	Backward Caste	70	38.89
4	Other	20	11.11
Total		180	100.00

Source: Field Survey.

Table 2 Age of the Respondents

Sl. No.	Age (Years)	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	10 – 20	12	6.67
2	20 – 30	33	18.33
3	30 – 40	56	31.11
4	40 – 50	37	20.55
5	50 – 60	39	21.67
6	60 and above	03	1.67
Total		180	100.00

Source: Field Server

Note: The average age of the respondents is found to be 38 years.

Table 3 Education Pattern of the Respondents

Sl. No.	Education Pattern	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Illiteracy	26	14.44
2	Just literacy	23	12.79
3	Primary Education	63	35.00
4	Secondary Education	26	14.44
5	Higher Education	15	8.33
6	Other	27	15.00
Total		180	100.00

Source: Field Survey.

Table 4 Reasons for Joining Self-Help Groups for Women Members

Sl. No.	Reasons for Joining Self-help Groups	No. of women members	Percentage
1	Cultivating Saving habit	36	20.00
2	To increase family income	53	29.44
3	To avail loans for business activities	46	25.56
4	To enhance socio-economic conditions of family	45	25.00
Total		180	100.00

Source: Field Survey.

Table 5 Occupation of the Respondents during the Pre-Self Help Groups

Sl. No	Occupation	No. Respondents	Percentage
1	House Wife	22	12.22
2	Agricultural labour	94	52.22
3	Petty business	12	6.68
4	Animal Husbandry	46	25.55
5	Sheep rearing	06	3.33
Total		180	100.00

Source: Field Survey.

Table 6 Occupation of the Respondents the post Self-Help Groups

Sl. No.	Occupation	No. Respondents	Percentage
1	House Wife	06	3.33
2	Agricultural labour	46	25.57
3	Petty Business	26	14.44
4	Animal Husbandry	82	45.55
5	Sheep rearing	20	11.11
Total		180	100.00

Source: Field Survey.

Table 7 Working Hours of the Respondents per day during the Pre-Self-Help Groups

Sl. No.	Working Hours	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	0 – 2	64	35.55
2	2 – 4	37	20.55
3	4 – 6	31	17.22
4	6 – 8	25	13.90
5	8 and above	23	12.78
Total		180	100.00

Source: Field Survey.

Note: The average working hours of the respondents is found to be 3 hours.

Table 8 Working Hours of the Respondents per day during the Post-Self-Help Groups

Sl. No	Working Hours	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	0 – 2	32	17.78
2	2 – 4	37	20.55
3	4 – 6	61	33.90
4	6 – 8	42	23.33
5	8 and above	08	4.44
Total		180	100.00

Source: Field Survey.

Note: The average working hours of the respondents is found to be 5 hours.

Economic Empowerment

Table 9 Income of the Respondents per month during the pre-Self-Help Groups

Sl. No.	Income	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Less than 1000	18	10.00
2	1000 – 2000	30	16.67
3	2000 – 3000	43	23.90
4	3000 – 4000	48	26.66
5	4000 – 5000	39	21.66
6	5000 and above	02	1.11
Total		180	100.00

Source: Field Survey.

Note: The average income of the respondents is found to be Rs.2,866/-.

Table 10 Income of the Respondents per month during the post Self Help Groups

Sl. No.	Income Monthly	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Less than 1000	16	8.90
2	1000 – 2000	18	10.00
3	2000 – 3000	40	22.22
4	3000 – 4000	39	21.67
5	4000 – 5000	48	26.66
6	5000 and above	19	10.55
Total		180	100.00

Source: Field Survey.

Note: The average income of the respondents is found to be Rs.3,288/-

Social Empowerment

Table 11 Social Empowerment of Women Through Self-Help Groups

Sl. No.	Particulars	Pre – Joining Self-Help Groups		Post – Joining Self-Help Groups	
		Number of women members	Percentage	Number of women members	Percentage
1	Recognition by family	18	20.22	60	33.33
2	Participation in community events	22	24.71	27	15.00
3	Involvement in social problems	38	42.70	41	22.27
4	Participating in government events	11	12.37	52	28.90
Total		89	100.00	180	100.00

Source: Field Survey.

Table 12 Cultural Empowerment of Women Through SHQS

Sl. No.	Particulars	Pre – Joining Self-Help Groups		Post – Joining Self-Help Groups	
		Number of women members	Percentage	Number of women members	Percentage
1	Participating in cultural functions	39	21.66	62	34.44
2	Participating in religious functions	28	15.55	58	32.22
3	Cultivating cultural values	65	36.11	28	15.55
4	Attending religious meetings	48	26.68	32	17.79
Total		180	100.00	180	100.00

Source: Field Survey.

Summary of the Major Findings of Study

Following is the summary of the major findings with regard to the socio-economic characteristics the respondents.

1. As many as 38 percent of the respondents belongs to backward caste and 33 percent schedule caste, 16 percent scheduled tribe and 11 percent others.
2. All the respondents are in the productive age group of 38 years.
3. As many as 35 percent respondents studies up to primary education and 15 percent as followed by higher education, 14 percent illiteracy and secondary education.
4. As many as 52.22 Percent of respondents primary occupation was agriculture labour and 22.55 percent animal husbandry, 12.22 percent housewife and meager percent 6.68 percent petty business and 3.33 percent sheep rearing during the pre-self-help groups.
5. There is a major change as many as 25.57 percent respondents occupation is agriculture labour, 45.55 percent animal husbandry, 14.44 percent petty business, 11.11 percent sheep rearing, very meager 6 percent of the respondents is housewife during post self-help-groups.
6. As many as 35.55 percent of the respondents work between 0-2 hours, 20.55 percent of the respondents work for 2-4 hours, 17.22 percent of the respondents work for 4-6 hours, 13.90 percent of the respondents work for 6-8 hours and 12.78 percent of the respondents work for more than 8 hours per day during pre-self-help groups.

7. The majority of respondents (33.90 percent) work for 4-6 hours, 4.44 percent of the respondents work for more than 8 hours, 23.33 percent of the respondents work for 6-8 hours, 20.55 percent of the respondents work for 2-4 hours, 17.78 percent of the respondents work for less than 2 hours per day during the post self-help groups.
8. As many as 26.66 percent of the respondents income per month not exceed Rs.4000/- and 10 percent of the respondents income less than Rs.1000/- and meager 1.11 percent of the respondents income is above Rs.5000/- per month during the pre-self-help groups.
9. As many as 26.66 percent of the respondents income per month is more than Rs.4000/- and 8 percent of the respondents income less than Rs.1000/- and major 10.55 percent of the respondents income is above Rs.5000/- per month in during the post self-help groups.
10. Present all the respondents are satisfied with the policy of the government regard to social and cultural empowerment of self-help groups.

Conclusion

The various development initiatives strategies, schemes and programmes which were implemented during different plan period with large outlays for all-round development of women produced substantial results which improved their socio-economic conditions to a great extent. Particularly, the women welfare interventions have brought about radical transformation in the conditions of women of both rural and urban areas. But the scheme also suffers from many organizational difficulties, there is need for identifying suitable and viable trades, depending on the local resources, skills and markets.

In the present scenario the self-help groups are not playing an active role in women empowerment and overall group activities have stagnant, because of the government political strategies and policies to become into power. These strategies leads to the cause of destructive of sustainable development not only on self-help groups and also directly or indirectly on other developmental programmes and policies of central and state government. Therefore, the Central Government and the institutional agencies have not come forward to support to total loans waive with regard to self-help groups. Hence, keeping view of the present situation, Government should evolve concrete and comprehensive policy after holding discussion both with the Central Government and institutional agencies for achieving desired results and to attain resources among the self-help groups women.

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